

BREAKING BOUNDARIES: EULER-MARUYAMA METHODOLOGY FOR UNCERTAIN STOCHASTIC SYSTEMS OF THE FIRST ORDER

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Abstract: Dynamical systems, serving as indispensable tools for modeling complex phenomena, find widespread application in diverse fields such as biology, engineering, physics, and finance. These systems, characterized by their time-dependent nature, are foundational in understanding the evolving dynamics of various processes. This study delves into the intricate realm of dynamical systems, with a particular focus on addressing uncertainties that inherently influence their behavior. Two primary forms of uncertainty emerge as pivotal factors in the study of dynamical systems: randomness and belief degree. These uncertainties add layers of complexity to the modeling process, requiring specialized mathematical frameworks. To tackle the stochastic nature of certain systems, the stochastic differential equation (SDE) emerges as a crucial class of differential equations. SDEs provide a robust methodology for capturing and analyzing the inherent randomness prevalent in dynamic processes. On the other front, another significant class of differential equations, the uncertain differential equation (UDE), comes into play when dealing with dynamical systems influenced primarily by belief degrees. Belief degrees introduce a subjective aspect to uncertainties, reflecting varying levels of confidence or belief in the evolving dynamics. UDEs, tailored to model these scenarios, provide a mathematical foundation for addressing uncertainties stemming from subjective beliefs. This abstract aims to highlight the pivotal roles played by stochastic and uncertain differential equations in modeling dynamical systems. Through a comprehensive exploration of SDEs and UDEs, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of how randomness and belief degrees individually shape the intricate dynamics of systems across different disciplines. The practical implications of this research extend across various domains. In biology, where processes often exhibit unpredictable behavior, the application of SDEs proves instrumental. In contrast, UDEs find application in scenarios such as decision-making processes, where uncertainties arise from subjective beliefs. The engineering field benefits from a combined approach, utilizing both SDEs and UDEs to address diverse uncertainties in system dynamics. Physics, with its intricate phenomena, gains a more accurate representation through the nuanced description provided by these differential equations. Furthermore, in the domain of finance, where the dynamics of markets are influenced by both stochastic elements and subjective beliefs, the application of SDEs and UDEs becomes indispensable. In conclusion, this abstract provides a comprehensive overview of the role of differential equations in modeling dynamical systems, emphasizing the distinct contributions of stochastic and uncertain differential equations in addressing randomness and belief degrees, respectively.

Keywords: Dynamical Systems, Stochastic Differential Equations (SDEs), Uncertain Differential Equations (UDEs), Randomness, Belief Degrees

INTRODUCTION

The significance of differential equations in modeling dynamical systems cuts across biology, engineering, physics, and finance, etc. In simple term, dynamical systems are time-dependent systems. Two forms of uncertainty are identified to be associated with dynamical systems, which are randomness

and belief degree. The class of differential equations that model dynamical systems associated with randomness only is known as the stochastic differential equation (SDE). While the class of differential equation that models dynamical systems associated with belief degrees only is known as uncertain differential equations (UDE). The foundation for SDEs is probability theory which started from the work of Kolmogorov (1933), and has since evolved, and studied by different scholars including Bachelier (1900), Black and Scholes (1973), Merton (1973), Hull and White (1990) and Dmouj (2006). Since the ground breaking work of the Japanese mathematician, Ito Kiyoshi in 1949 on stochastic processes' differentiation and integration, SDEs have been successfully applied by different researchers when it comes to discussing the modeling of dynamical systems. As an example, in financial processes, Black and Scholes (1973) won the Nobel Prize in economics for successfully using this concept to price options in their model. On the other hand, the UDE was first mentioned by Liu (2009) sequel to the ground breaking work of Liu (2007) which birthed uncertainty theory. Since then, researchers have followed in expanding the boundaries of knowledge in this new branch of mathematics. UDEs have been successfully applied in describing the evolution of dynamical systems. For example, Liu (2009) proposed an uncertain stock model for option pricing. Overtime as researchers continue in study, it was observed that the two forms of uncertainty (randomness and belief degree) can simultaneously drive a dynamical system. As a result, a new class of differential equations called as uncertain stochastic differential equations was created. As a result, a new class of differential equations called uncertain stochastic differential equations (USDE) was created. Just as the SDEs are modeled by probability theory and the UDEs by uncertainty theory, the USDEs are modeled by chance theory. The USDEs are driven by uncertain random processes, which are a collection of uncertain random variables. Chance theory came into being through the work of Liu (2013a), where he introduced the concept of chance measure by combining uncertain and probability measures. Researchers have studied this new concept of chance theory, and have equally contributed to its development over these years. Using probability and uncertainty distribution, Liu (2013b) provided a method for determining an uncertain random variable's expected value as well as a definition of their law of operation. Fei (2014) combined the $\hat{I}^{\alpha}$ integral and Liu integral into the $\hat{I}^{\alpha}$ -Liu integral to integrate an uncertain random process. He also provided the $\hat{I}^{\alpha}$ -Liu formula for finding the derivative of the hybrid process. Like the SDEs and UDEs, the USDEs have also been successfully applied in describing dynamical systems. Matenda and Chikodza (2018) suggested an uncertain stochastic stock model with jump using an USDE. They also outlined the analytical solutions to some USDE. The exact and analytical solutions to USDEs are not easily solved and do not exist for some. However, it is possible to approximate the solution numerically, just as with SDEs and UDEs. Hence to address this challenge, it is necessary to create algorithms to numerically solve USDEs. Chirima et al. (2020) used the Runge-Kutta of order four (RK4) to numerically solve USDEs. In order to use numerical schemes of solving ODEs for USDEs, they converted the USDEs into ODEs with α -path, whose solution is a contour process. They also gave the theorems and proofs for existence, uniqueness and stability of USDEs. Alternatively, the Euler-Maruyama (EM) method is used to numerically solve USDEs in this paper. The EM method is applied to calculate the stock price of an uncertain stochastic market, and the results are compared to that of RK4 proposed by Chirima et al. (2020). One idea this paper contributes is using the EM method to solve USDEs. In preparation for the main work of this paper, the next section presents some basic definitions of useful terms. In the following section, we present the uncertain stochastic differential equation (USDE) and the theorems for their existence, uniqueness and stability. In the numerical example section we use the EM technique with α -path to compute the price of the stock from a considered stock model of an uncertain random market. We also show the results in table and figures. In the final section, conclusions are given.

PRELIMINARIES

We present some preliminary material which will be of use later on.

Stochastic analysis

Stochastic process

Definition 2.1: A stochastic process is a function:

$Y_t(\psi): T \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}) \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ such that $\{Y_t \in B\}$ is an event for any Borel set B at each time t . Where $(\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$ is a probability space and T is a totally ordered set.

Definition 2.2 (Brownian motion/Wiener process): A stochastic process B_t is called a standard Brownian motion or Wiener process if it satisfies the following properties i. $B_0 = 0$ and almost all sample paths are continuous, ii. B_t has stationary and independent increments, iii. every increment $B_{s+t} - B_t$ is a normal random variable with expected value 0 and variance t .

Stochastic differential equation

Definition 2.3. The differential equation: $dY_t =$

$m(t, Y_t)dt + n(t, Y_t)dB_t$ is called a stochastic differential equation. Where, B_t is a standard Brownian motion and m and n are two given functions. An Ito process Y_t that satisfies the equation about identically in t is called the solution of the stochastic differential equation.

Uncertain analysis

Uncertain process

Definition 2.4. An uncertain process is a function: $Y_t(\pi): T \times (\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ such that $\{Y_t \in B\}$ is an event for any Borel set B at each time t . Where $(\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U})$ is an uncertainty space, and T is a totally ordered set.

Contour process

Definition 2.5: Let Y_t be an uncertain process. If for each $\alpha \in (0,1)$, there exist a real function Y_t^α such that $\mathcal{M}\{Y_t \leq Y_t^\alpha, \forall t\} = \alpha$ $\mathcal{M}\{Y_t > Y_t^\alpha, \forall t\} = 1 - \alpha$ then Y_t is called a contour process. In this case, Y_t^α is called an α -path of the contour process Y_t .

Theorem 2.6: (Yao and Chen, 2013) Let Y_t be an uncertain process with an α -path Y_t^α . Then Y_t has an inverse uncertainty distribution

$$\Phi^{-1}(\alpha) = Y_t^\alpha, \forall \alpha \in (0, 1)$$

This theorem is also known as the inverse uncertainty distribution theorem of a contour process.

Definition 2.7: An uncertain process L_t is said to be a canonical Liu process if:

i. $L_0 = 0$ and almost all sample paths are Lipschitz continuous, ii. L_t has stationary and independent increments, iii. every increment $L_{s+t} - L_t$ is a normal random variable with expected value 0 and variance t^2 .

Definition 2.8: The inverse uncertainty distribution of the canonical Liu process is given by

$$\Phi^{-1}(\alpha) = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \ln \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$$

Uncertain differential equation

Definition 2.8: The differential equation

$$dY_t = m(t, Y_t)dt + n(t, Y_t)dL_t \quad (1)$$

is called an uncertain differential equation. Where, L_t is a canonical Liu process and m and n are two given functions. A Liu process Y_t that satisfies Equation 1 identically in t is known as the solution of the uncertain differential equation. The uncertain differential equation defined above is equivalent to the uncertain integral equation

$$Y_s = Y_0 + \int_0^s m(t, Y_t)dt + \int_0^s n(t, Y_t)dL_t \quad 0$$

Chance theory

We shall be presenting previous literatures developed on chance theory that are important to this study.

Definition 2.9: A chance space is defined as the product space $(\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$, where $(\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U})$ is an uncertainty space and $(\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$ is a probability space.

Definition 2.10: Given a chance space $(\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$ and an uncertain random event $\Phi \in \mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{A}$, the chance measure $\mathcal{C}$ of Φ is defined by

$$\mathcal{C}\{\Phi\} = \int_0^1 \mathcal{P}\{\psi \in \Psi \mid \mathcal{U}\{\pi \in \Pi \mid (\pi, \psi) \in \Phi\} \geq x\} dx$$

A chance measure satisfies the following properties:

1. (Liu, 2013b) Normality: $\mathcal{C}\{\Pi \times \Psi\} = 1, \mathcal{C}\{\emptyset\} = 0$

2. (Liu, 2013b) Monotonicity: $\mathcal{C}\{\Phi_1\} \leq \mathcal{C}\{\Phi_2\}$ for any event

$$\Phi_1 \subset \Phi_2$$

3. (Liu, 2013b) Self-duality: $\mathcal{C}\{\Phi\} + \mathcal{C}\{\Phi^c\} = 1$ for any event Φ

4. (Hou, 2014) Sub-additivity: For any countable sequence of events $\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots,$

$$\mathcal{C}\left\{\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} \Phi_i\right\} \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathcal{C}\{\Phi_i\}$$

5. (Hou, 2014) Null-additivity: Suppose $\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots,$ are a sequence of events with $\mathcal{C}\{\Phi_i\} \rightarrow 0$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$. Then for any event $\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{C}\{\Phi \cup \Phi_i\} = \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{C}\{\Phi \setminus \Phi_i\} =$

$\mathcal{C}\{\Phi\}$ That means $\mathcal{C}\{\Phi_1 \cup \Phi_2\} = \mathcal{C}\{\Phi_1\} + \mathcal{C}\{\Phi_2\}$ if either

$\mathcal{C}\{\Phi_1\} = 0$ or $\mathcal{C}\{\Phi_2\} = 0$

6. (Hou, 2014) Asymptotic: For any sequence of events

$\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots, \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{C}\{\Phi_i\} > 0$, if $\Phi_i \uparrow \Pi \times \Psi$

$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{C}\{\Phi_i\} < 0$, if $\Phi_i \downarrow \emptyset$

$i \rightarrow \infty$

Definition 2.11: Given a chance space $(\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$, an uncertain random variable is defined as a function $\zeta : (\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}) \rightarrow B \in \mathfrak{R}$ such that $\zeta \in B \in (\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{A})$.

Definition 2.12: Given a chance space $(\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$ and a totally ordered set T , an uncertain random process is a function:

$Y_t(\pi, \psi) : T \times (\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}) \rightarrow \mathfrak{R}$ such that $Y_t \in B \in (\mathcal{B} \times \mathcal{A})$ for any Borel set $B(\mathfrak{R})$ at each time t .

Remark 1: Suppose Y_t and Z_t are uncertain and stochastic processes, respectively, then $X_t = m(Y_t, Z_t)$ is an uncertain random process given a measurable function f .

Definition 2.13: Given fixed $\pi^* \in \Pi$ and $\psi^* \in \Psi$, the sample path of an uncertain random process Y_t on a chance space $(\Pi, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{U}) \times (\Psi, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P})$ is defined as the function $Y_t(\pi^*, \psi^*)$.

Ito-Liu integral

Definition 2.14: (Fei, 2014) Let $Y_t = (F_t, G_t)$ be an uncertain stochastic process. For any partition $P = \{a = t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{k+1} = b\}$ of the closed interval $[a, b]$ with $a = t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_{k+1} = b$ the mesh is written as $\Delta = \max_{1 \leq i \leq k} |t_{i+1} - t_i|$. Then the Ito-Liu integral of Y_t with respect to $K_t = (B_t, L_t)$ is defined as follows,

$$\int_a^b Y_s dK_s = \lim_{\Delta \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^N G_{t_i} (B_{t_{i+1}} - B_{t_i}) + \lim_{\Delta \rightarrow 0} \sum_{i=1}^N F_{t_i} (L_{t_{i+1}} - L_{t_i})$$

provided that exists in mean square and is an uncertain random variable, where L_t and B_t are a one-dimensional canonical process and a one-dimensional Brownian motion, respectively. Here, Y_t is called Ito-Liu integrable. In particular, when $Y_t \equiv 0$, Y_t is called Liu integrable.

Theorem 2.15 (Fei, 2014): Let $B = (B_t)_{0 \leq t \leq T} =$

$(B_{t_1}, \dots, B_{t_m})_{T_0 \leq t \leq T}$ and $L = (L_t)_{0 \leq t \leq T} = (L_{1t}, \dots, L_{nt})_{T_0 \leq t \leq T}$ be an

M-dimensional standard Brownian motion and an n-dimensional canonical process, respectively. Assume that uncertain stochastic processes $Y_1(t), Y_2(t), \dots, Y_p(t)$ are given by:

$$dY_k(t) = u_k(t)dt + \sum_{l=1}^m v_{kl}(t)dB_t^l + \sum_{l=1}^n w_{kl}(t)dL_t^l, \quad k = 1, \dots, p$$

Where $u_k(t)$ are all absolute integrable uncertain stochastic processes, $v_{kl}(t)$ are all square integrable uncertain stochastic processes, and $w_{kl}(t)$ are all Liu integrable uncertain stochastic processes. For $k, l = 1, \dots, p$, let

$$\frac{\partial K}{\partial t}(t, y_1, \dots, y_p), \frac{\partial K}{\partial y_k}(t, y_1, \dots, y_p), \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial y_k \partial y_l}(t, y_1, \dots, y_p)$$

be continuous functions. Then we have:

$$\begin{aligned} dK(t, Y_1(t), \dots, Y_p(t)) &= \frac{\partial K}{\partial t}(t, Y_1(t), \dots, Y_p(t))dt \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^p \frac{\partial K}{\partial y_k}(t, Y_1(t), \dots, Y_p(t))dY_k(t) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=1}^p \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial y_k \partial y_l}(t, Y_1(t), \dots, Y_p(t))dY_k(t)dY_l(t) \end{aligned}$$

where $dB_t^k dB_t^l = \delta_{kl}dt$, $dB_t^k dt = dL_t^i dL_t^j = dL_t^i dt = dB_t^k dL_t^i = 0$, for $k, l = 1, \dots, m$, $i, j = 1, \dots, n$. Here:

$$\delta_{kl} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } k \neq l \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

UNCERTAIN STOCHASTIC DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

This new class of differential equation is driven by both the Brownian motion and Liu canonical process.

Definition 3.1: The differential equation

$$dY = m(t, Y_t)dt + n(t, Y_t)dL_t + r(t, Y_t)dB_t \quad (3)$$

is called an Uncertain Stochastic Differential Equation (USDE). Where L_t and B_t are one-dimensional canonical process and Brownian motion, respectively, and m, n and r are given functions.

Remark 2: The solution to the USDE above is called an uncertain stochastic process Y_t .

Existence and uniqueness

Theorem 3.2 (Chirima et al., 2020): An USDE:

$$dY_t = m(t, Y_t)dt + n(t, Y_t)dL_t + r(t, Y_t)dB_t$$

satisfying the linear growth and Lipschitz conditions

$$|m(x, t)| + |n(x, t)| + |r(x, t)| \leq L(1 + |x|), \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}, t \geq 0$$

And $|m(x, t) - m(y, t)| + |n(x, t) - n(y, t)| + |r(x, t) - r(y, t)| \leq L|x - y|, \quad \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}, t \geq 0$ respectively, for some constant L , is said to have a unique solution that is sample continuous.

Stability

Definition 3.3: An arbitrary USDE is said to be stable, if given any two solutions to an uncertain stochastic differential equation, Y_t and Z_t which satisfy the condition

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} C \{ |Y_t - Z_t| > \epsilon \} = 0, \quad \forall t \geq 0, |Y_0 - Z_0| \rightarrow 0$$

Theorem 3.4: (Chirima et al., 2020) If v_t, μ_t and ν_t are continuous functions where $\int_0^s v_t dt < +\infty, \int_0^s |\mu_t| dt < +\infty, \int_0^s |\nu_t| dt < +\infty$ then an USDE $dY_t = v_t Y_t dt + \mu_t Y_t dL_t + \nu_t Y_t dB_t$ is stable.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

Matenda and Chikodza (2018) proposed an uncertain stochastic stock model for the stock price Z_t and bond price Y_t : $\{ dY_t = aY_t dt$

$$(2)$$

$$dZ_t = bZ_t dt + \sigma_2 Z_t dL_t + \sigma_1 Z_t dB_t$$

where a represents the rate of riskless interest, b represents the drift of the stock, σ_2 represents the uncertain diffusion and the random diffusion is represented by σ_1 .

For an USDE of Equation (2), let $T = 1$, $b = 0.06$, $Z_0 = 40$, $\sigma_1 = 0.29$, $\sigma_2 = 0.32$, $N = 100$. Our aim is to use the EM method to compute the distribution of the price of stock Z_t and compare our result with that exact solution and RK4 proposed by Chirima et al. (2020). Equations (2) and (1) are similar, with α -path

$dZ_t^\alpha = bZ_t^\alpha dt + |\sigma_2 Z_t^\alpha| \Phi^{-1}(\alpha) dt + \sigma_1 Z_t^\alpha dB_t$ (3) which is an SDE α -path whose solution Z_t is a stochastic contour process. $\Phi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is deterministic and represents the inverse uncertainty distribution of the canonical Liu process given by:

$$\Phi^{-1}(\alpha) = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \ln \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha}$$

In Equation (2), eliminating $\sigma_1 Z_t dB_t$ leaves us with the Liu's stock model proposed by Liu (2013).

$$dZ_t = bZ_t dt + \sigma_2 Z_t dL_t \quad (4)$$

Also, eliminating $\sigma_2 Z_t dL_t$ in Equation (2) leaves us with the Black-Scholes (1973) model.

$$dZ_t = bZ_t dt + \sigma_1 Z_t dB_t \quad (5)$$

We will proceed to solve Equation (3) by the EM method using MATLAB.

Euler-Maruyama method with α -path

Consider the stochastic initial value problem:

$dY(t) = m(Y(t))dt + n(Y(t))dL_t + r(Y(t))dB(t)$ and the SDE with α -path is given as

$$dY^\alpha(t) = m(Y^\alpha(t))dt + |n(Y^\alpha(t))| \Phi^{-1}(\alpha) dt + r(Y^\alpha(t))dB(t) \quad (6)$$

with

$Y^\alpha(0) = Y_0^\alpha$ (Y_0^α is an uncertain random variable) and $0 \leq$

$t \leq T$. Before applying a numerical method to the initial value problem, we first discretize the time interval by letting $\Delta t = T/L$ for some positive integer L and $\tau_j = j\Delta t$ (Higham, 2001). Note that $Y^\alpha(\tau_j)$ will be approximated by

Y_j^α .

The Euler-Maruyama method for the SDE with α -path is given by

$$Y_j^\alpha = Y_{j-1}^\alpha + m(Y_{j-1}^\alpha)\Delta t + |n(Y_{j-1}^\alpha)| \Phi^{-1}(\alpha)\Delta t + r(Y_{j-1}^\alpha)(B(\tau_j) - B(\tau_{j-1})) \quad (7)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, L$. (Higham, 2001). Taking $n = 0$ yields the generally known stochastic case without uncertainty in the system. Taking $h = 0$ yields the uncertainty case without randomness in the system as proposed by Liu (2009).

Algorithm

The EM method below can be used in solving USDEs.

$$Y_j^\alpha = Y_{j-1}^\alpha + m(Y_{j-1}^\alpha)\Delta t + |n(Y_{j-1}^\alpha)| \Phi^{-1}(\alpha)\Delta t + r(Y_{j-1}^\alpha)(B(\tau_j) - B(\tau_{j-1}))$$

Let T be a fixed time length, N be the number of iterations, and $dt = T/N$ be the interval difference over $[0, T]$. We choose the step size dt as an integer multiple

$R \geq 1$, that is, $DT = R * dt$, and $L = N/R$.

In this case, we choose $R = 1$. We calculate our own discretized Brownian pathways and utilize them to produce the increments. $B(\tau_j) - B(\tau_{j-1})$ needed in Equation (7).

Step 1. Set $\alpha = 0.05$ and $j = 1$.

Step 2. Solve Equation (6) using EM method Equation (7).

Step 3. Increase j by 1 and repeat steps 2 and 3 to the maximum value of N .

Step 4. Obtain $E(Y_s^\alpha)$ by $\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N Y_j}{N}$

Step 5. The process is repeated for α values 0.05, 0.10, 0.15... 0.95. This brings us to the inverse uncertainty distribution of Y_t .

From Table 1 and Figure 1, the EM method yields the least stock prices compared to RK4 and exact methods. The stock prices from RK4 prove to converge faster to those from the exact method as seen in the enlarged view of Figure 1 in Figure 2. Thus showing the RK4 method has faster rate of convergence than the EM method.

At $\alpha = 0.5$, the EM method to the USDE model gives exactly the same stock price as that for the BlackScholes (1973) SDE model. This can be easily seen from Figures 4 and 5. It implies that at $\alpha = 0.5$, the uncertain component is eliminated from the USDE thereby turning the USDE stock model into the Black-Scholes (1973) SDE stock model, which further proves that the USDE is indeed a hybrid of the UDE and SDE. The randomness of the USDE model can also be easily seen from Figures 3, 4, 5, and 6. The distributions represent the stock price Z_t for USDE using EM, RK4 and analytical methods. An uncertain distribution is regular if it satisfies the conditions of continuity, strictly increasing, and $\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} \Phi(x) = 0, \lim_{x \rightarrow +\infty} \Phi(x) = 1$

(Liu 2010).

(Liu 2010).

From Table 1, the results of EM and RK4 method satisfies the above conditions. The results in Figure 1 shows that the functions are increasing for both the EM

Table 1. Stock prices (Z_t) for uncertain stochastic market based on analytical method, Euler-Maruyama method and Runge-Kutta of order 4 method for α values.

α -path	Stock Price		
	Analytical method	EM method	RK4 method
0.05	25.265	24.524	24.617
0.15	31.276	29.580	30.474
0.20	33.258	31.292	32.406
0.25	34.990	32.805	34.093
0.30	36.576	34.206	35.638
0.35	38.079	35.547	37.103
0.40	39.541	36.864	38.528
0.45	40.996	38.185	39.945
0.50	42.473	39.539	41.385
0.55	44.004	40.954	42.876
0.60	45.623	42.465	44.454

0.65	47.375	44.116	46.161
0.70	49.322	45.970	48.058
0.75	51.558	48.124	50.236
0.80	54.242	50.744	52.852
0.85	57.680	54.155	56.201
0.90	62.586	59.126	60.981
0.95	71.404	68.362	69.574

Source: Author, 2023

Figure 1. Distribution curves for stock prices in the uncertain stochastic market based on the EM, RK4 and analytical methods.

Source: Author, 2023

Figure 2. Enlarged section of Figure 1.

Source: Author, 2023

Euler-Maruyama Approximation of the USDE at $\alpha=0.3$

Figure 3. The simulation of stock price at $\alpha = 0.3$.

Source: Author, 2023

Euler-Maruyama Approximation of the USDE at $\alpha=0.5$

Figure 4. The simulation of stock price at $\alpha = 0.5$.

Source: Author, 2023

Euler-Maruyama Approximation of the SDE

Figure 5. The simulation of stock price without uncertainty component.

Source: Author, 2023

Figure 6. The simulation of stock price at $\alpha = 0.7$.

Source: Author, 2023

Figure 7. The simulation of stock price at $\alpha = 0$ or $\alpha = 1$. Source: Author, 2023

And RK4 methods, except at $\Phi(x) \equiv 0$ and $\Phi(x) \equiv 1$, necessary and sufficient conditions by Peng and Iwamura which can be seen from Figure 7, further supporting the (2013).

Conclusion

We have demonstrated in this paper that USDEs can be converted to SDEs with α -paths and solved by the Euler-Maruyama method. The solution of the SDEs with α -path therefore becomes a stochastic contour process. The RK4 converges faster than the EM method to the exact solution. The EM method proved to yield lower stock price compared to the stock price from the RK4 and exact methods. At $\alpha = 0.5$, the USDE crashed to the SDE with the uncertain component eliminated showing that the USDE is indeed a hybrid of the UDE and SDE.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interest.

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